

Spiritual and Moral Factors of Educating Young Students in the Spirit of Religious Tolerance and International Harmony

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Abstract: in this article, didactic mechanisms of formation of the sense of personal responsibility, the foundations of religious tolerance and education are applied to the educational process. Based on the values collected by the ancestors over the centuries, formation of a harmonious attitude towards representatives of other nations, humanization of education, awareness of national identity, development of social relations and cooperation, competences of using moral educational scientific heritages are enlightened by means of pedagogical influence.

Keywords: outlook, development, religion, education, personality, responsibility, ability, perfection, spiritual and moral qualities, didactics.

At the center of any reforms carried out in the society, the future of the young generation, which is the future of the country, and its growth as a mature staff is put forward as the main task. For example, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2020 in his address to the chambers of the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan focused on the issue of youth and generation: "As we aim to make Uzbekistan a developed country, this requires not only rapid reforms we achieve with knowledge and innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate new generation personnel who will be enterprising reformers, who think strategically, and who will be educated and qualified." past

Therefore, the Greek historian Herodotus, who lived around 484-431/425 BC during the formation of human history, contains information about the educational activities of the ancient Persians, Sakas, and Massagetae. Bravery is what the Persians are most proud of, and they are proud of their sons. The king sent gifts to whoever had a son. From the age of five, children were taught to ride a horse, shoot a bow, be honest and speak correctly. The conditions themselves taught the children to ride a horse, to shoot with a bow, they were directed to bring up the qualities of courage, correctness, heroism, to be the protector of their people.

In the analysis of the historical sources that have reached us, in the determination of the ideas of national and inter-ethnic harmony, in the epics about the national heroes that each nation loves, the desire for the Motherland and freedom, sacrificing one's life for the motherland and one's tribe, honor, honor feelings of struggle for honor are expressed. In particular, brave patriots such as Tomaris, Shiroq, great heroes Rustam, Siyovush, Alpomish depicted in epic

works also love their nation and homeland. A great sense of duty, sacrificing one's life for the Motherland and people, and enduring any hardships are their main educational qualities. The main qualities of folk heroes are courage and bravery.

Including "New Uzbekistan. In goals 71-74, 82 of the "Development Strategy", it is very important that the tasks of further acceleration of work in this field are placed at the level of state importance. Goal 71: To turn a healthy worldview and creativity into a national movement in society by widely promoting the idea of "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development" based on the principle of goodness and humanity.

Implementation of the concept of "New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society". Organization of legal-educational activities on the formation of legal culture among the population in harmony with the teaching of the rich history, scientific-cultural heritage, national-religious values of our people. To develop effective, creative and innovative methods of organizing promotional activities and to take measures for their timely implementation. State support for the preservation, popularization and development of the national values and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people. Ensuring the integrity of spiritual education in the family, educational organizations and neighborhoods. Preventing the spread of false information by providing unbiased information on time in mass media and social networks. Based on the principle of "neighborhood-district-province-republic" formation of a map of optimization of the socio-spiritual environment in the regions, wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in this process. Development of scientifically based indicators for evaluation of spiritual education. Application of interactive methods of education to make schools a center of true spirituality and enlightenment, culture. Forming the ability to fight together against ideological attacks on the basis of the national idea, to strengthen family, school and neighborhood cooperation and to ensure the integrity of spiritual education on this basis. To ensure the realization of the idea of "New Uzbekistan - Third Renaissance" under the slogan "Youth - creators of New Uzbekistan".

Goal 74: To strengthen the environment of inter-ethnic harmony and inter-religious tolerance in the society.

Further improvement of the state support system for national cultural centers. Ensuring consistent implementation of the state policy concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of international relations. Creating additional favorable conditions for young people of different nationalities, raising the awareness of civic duty, patriotism, and the culture of interethnic interaction based on tolerance. Taking measures to provide additional support from the state to mass media operating in foreign languages and covering state policy in the field of inter-ethnic relations. Improving the activities of friendship societies in order to develop friendly relations with foreign countries.

Goal 82: Formation of effective mechanisms for combating extremism and terrorism.

Implementation of an effective state policy to combat extremism and terrorism, which allows to ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens. Improving the preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing the factors that cause extremism and terrorism, improving the socio-spiritual environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas and eliminating their problems through systematic work with those who are influenced by them. Formation of strong and stable immunity of the population, especially the young generation, against the ideology of terrorism and extremism. Improving the international legal framework for combating extremism and terrorism and expanding the contractual legal framework for cooperation with foreign countries, regional and international organizations in the field of combating extremism and

terrorism. Strengthening the personnel capacity and resources of diplomatic missions and consular institutions, the Agency for Foreign Labor Migration, as well as other agencies that deal with citizens who go and live abroad for a long time. Exchange of information and experience with foreign countries and international organizations in the field of combating extremism, terrorism and their financing. Active participation in international and regional organizations whose activities are aimed at combating extremism and terrorism. Coordinating joint efforts to implement the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy in Central Asia within the framework of the joint action plan. Expanding the role of Uzbekistan in the implementation of international initiatives that facilitate the development of information exchange and cooperation within the framework of joint efforts to combat extremism and terrorism in Central Asia. Accelerate initiatives to attract the attention of the world community and regional organizations to ensure peace and harmony in Afghanistan and involve this country in regional cooperation processes, including the fight against extremism and terrorism.

In particular, even in ancient times, one of the national values of the people was training the national wrestlers, paying attention to the qualities of patriotism, bravery, and courage. Because wrestlers have always fought for the honor and glory of their people. That's why Nurota trainers, when teaching wrestling to wrestlers, start the first lesson with the story of wrestlers from the Castle of Nur, which is a clear proof of this 3. Our ancient ancestors greatly appreciated courage, justice, loyalty and humanity in a person. In the monuments of Orhun-Enasoy written down in the 6th century, noble ideas such as patriotism, unity, struggle to live as a union, bravery and courage were put forward through the martial activities, lifestyle, and characteristics of the Khokans and the Alps.

We are very serious about the issue of translating and publishing masterpieces of world literature into Uzbek, following the deeply meaningful principle of "literary friendship-eternal friendship" in educating young people who are the future of our country. we are paying attention. It should be noted that in our country, thousands and thousands of works, which are the priceless property of world literature, have been translated and found a place in the hearts of readers. In addition to this, promoting the best examples of our classical and modern literature in foreign languages, which for centuries have been glorifying immortal qualities such as perfect human education, just society, individual freedom, freedom of the Motherland, creativity, tolerance and internationalism, humanity. great work is being done in our country. In this regard, teaching in the Karakalpak, Russian, Tajik, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen languages along with the Uzbek language has been introduced in the educational institutions of our republic, English, French, German, Spanish in our higher educational institutions. , the fact that Japanese, Chinese, Korean, Arabic philology is taught as a special subject is gaining importance.

Since ancient times, our country is a land inhabited by different nations and peoples who believe in different religions and have different cultures, languages, customs, and lifestyles. Since the first years of independence, special attention has been paid to preserving the values of different religions in our country, creating the necessary conditions for all citizens to practice their faith, strengthening inter-religious and ethnic harmony, and developing ancient common traditions between them. Our Constitution states that "All citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, faith, personality and social status." is the ground created to further strengthen harmony and solidarity among our multi-ethnic nation.

In our country, all legal bases and necessary conditions have been created to ensure inter-

3Sadridinov B. Light Castle Wrestlers. Salvation newspaper. March 6, 2008.

ethnic and inter-religious harmony. Formation and further strengthening of the culture of tolerance has become one of the priorities of our state policy. The fifth priority of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 is "Ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, as well as thoughtful, mutually beneficial and practical priorities in the field of foreign policy". In the Declaration "On the Principles of Tolerance" adopted at the 28th session of the General Conference of UNESCO, it was emphasized that "without tolerance there can be no peace, and without peace there can be no development and democracy." folded

Nowadays, Uzbekistan is an example for the whole world in terms of religious tolerance and inter-religious dialogue. Citizens living in our republic, regardless of their religion, have been working together, in peaceful and peaceful conditions, for the development of our country. The basis of the law on freedom of conscience has been further improved in our country. Today in Uzbekistan, all conditions have been created for representatives of different religions to believe in their religion without any obstacles. It is known from history that the principles of religious tolerance are expressed in the life of any society, mutual respect and sincerity are established in that society, and all people live a peaceful and peaceful life. Just as there is no development and prosperity without peace, peace is not sustainable without religious tolerance.

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